

GOOD GOVERNANCE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT: A STUDY OF KUSHMANDI BLOCK OF DAKSHIN DINAJPUR (W.B) AND BETANATI BLOCK OF MAYURBHANJ (ODISHA)

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Abstract

We know that rural society demands highly setup of good governance and rural development in rural areas in India. Good governance and rural development issues are greatly related with living people in rural areas and the rural people who mostly demand the structure of good governance in the making of rural developmental process. In this paper I want to highlight the Good Governance and Rural Development: A Study of Kushmandi Block of Dakshin Dinajpur (W.B) and Betanati Block of Mayurbhanj (Odisha). Besides this I want to highlight some current rural development schemes and those functions in the study areas. The study emphasizes on the functioning and progress of rural development schemes in the study areas.

Keywords: *Good governance, Rural development, Schemes etc.*

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1.1 Introduction:

For the rural development the indicators of good governance as noted by the World Bank are similarly applicable. Specially the publications of the World Bank have identified four aspects of governance like., public sector management, accountability, legal framework for development and transparency. These four aspects bring massive change in the rural development sector. In Indian context government implemented the 73rd Constitutional amendment bill in 1993 for securing the all-round development in rural areas as well as the rural people in the country. In the 73rd constitutional amendment, the panchayat has been referred to as the local government as well as the local governance for securing the bright prospects to the rural India. The amendment can plan for economic development and social justice. The main purpose of this study is to examine the good governance through Rural Development Programmes in both blocks where the good governance plays the most

important role for rural development. Both of the blocks are dependent on good governance initiatives for development. Through this research work a brief overview of the role of good governance in rural development is analyzed and the planning structure of the particular area on Kushmandi block and Betanati block is emphasized.

1.2 Scope of the study: The study confined two rural blocks of W.B and Odisha. First one is Kushamndi block (consisting of eight gram panchayats) of Dakshin Dinajpur District in West Bengal and other one is Betanati block (consisting of twenty four gram panchayats) of Mayurbhanj district in Odisha.

1.3 Rural Development Schemes in Kushmandi Block (W.B): In this research work only five (5 nos.) rural development schemes highlighted for the study. The following schemes discussed given below:

1.3.1 ODF: ODF: means Open Defecation Free. This is a powerful project. The campaign was run to so that the common people of the village did not leave the excrement in the open space. All of the elected representatives of the panchayat, employees of the block administration, and employees of the district administration are associated with this powerful work. Even associated with the District Magistrate.

1.3.2 Role of ICDS in Kushmandi Block: The Integrated Child Development Service (Scheme) is a Govt. sponsored scheme running in the block for providing children and women the health facilities like; Supplementary nutrition, Pre-school, Early childhood care, education with curriculum of UNICEF, Health check-up, to provide Sishusathi scheme and other referral services. Under this scheme the 327 ICDS centres, 317 nos. Of helpers, 320 worker, 22,765 children and 4,205 mothers are getting benefits and the detailed report is given below:

G.P No.	Center no.	Helper	Worker	Child	Pregnant/ Lactating Mother.
1	42	41	41	2912	546
2	43	43	41	3467	663
3	43	41	43	3013	510
4	44	44	44	2792	518
5	35	33	34	2575	472
6	43	39	41	2784	503
7	33	32	32	1994	427
8	44	44	44	3228	566
Total	327	317	320	22,765	4,205

Table No. 01 (Source: Office of the ICDS, Kushmandi Block through data collection, date-22/07/23)

1.3.3 Health facilities in the Kushmandi Block through Rural Hospitals:

As there is a saying that “Health is Wealth”. To prove these words government of west Bengal under the Department of Health and Family welfare a number of rural and primary health centres have been established with a number of sub-centres in the Kushmandi Block.

These are given below:

Number of Gram panchayat	Number of Sub-centre	Number of Auxiliary Nurse Mobile	Number of Second Auxiliary Nurse Mobile.
1	4	4	3
2	4	4	4
3	4	3	3
4	4	4	2
5	3	3	2
6	4	4	4
7	3	3	2
8	4	4	2
Total	30	29	20

Table No. 02 (Source: Office of Kushmandi Block rural hospital through data collection, date-22/07/23)

1.3.4 Public Health Engineering (PHE): 2017

Water is supplied from PHE to rural areas. The objective of this project is to bring arsenic free water to the common people in rural areas. Three PHE projects have been implemented in the Kushmandi Block. Through this project, drinking water is provided to more than sixty thousands of people. Six crore rupees were allocated for implementing these three projects.

These are three projects:

Serial Number	Name of the Gram panchayat.	Location of PHE	Number of PHE	Benefitted Village
1	1 no. Akcha gram panchayat.	Goalgaon	1	20
2	2 no. Karange gram panchayat.	Makoil	1	20
3	6 no. Beroil gram panchayat.	Hasroil	1	20

Table No. 03 (Source: PHE, Balurghat; through data collection on 19.12.2017 & 24th May 2022)

1.3.5 National Social Assistance Programme: This can be categorised into three units:

1.3.5.1 Indira Gandhi Oldest Pension Schemes: Under this scheme who are above 60 years and below 79 years old, get Rs, 400 and those who are above 80 years old men get Rs. 1000 as monthly allowance. About 1265 nos. men and 1039 nos. women got this advantage in the Scheme in Kushmandi block those.

1.3.5.2 Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme: Under this scheme the widows upto the age 40years will get Rs 600 per month and those who have crossed the age of 40 year will get Rs 1000 as monthly Widow Allowance. 1543nos. of Widow got this facility under this scheme in Kushmandi block.

1.3.5.3 Indira Gandhi National Disabilities Pension Scheme: In this scheme 18% to 79% handicapped persons get Rs. 600/- per month as allowance and those who belong to 80% disability but crossed 80 years get Rs.1000/- per month in Kushmandi block.

1.4 Empirical study of Betanati Block: In this research work only five (5) rural development schemes have been selected for the study.

1.4.1 Health Facilities of Betanati Block: One (1) Community Health Centre (CHC) situated at Betanati block in Mayurbhanj district and this CHC only thirty (30) beds are available for the patients of Betanati block. This CHC is basically called rural hospital at Block level.

Figure of health facilities of Betanati block

SL No	Name of the PHC	Total Nos. PHC	Total Nos. Sub-Centre	Total Nos. ANM	Total Nos. ASHA	Total Village Covered
01	Jugol	1	10	11	52	52
02	Baisinga	1	10	8 (6 vacant)	66	66
03	Pinchhabania	1	9	6	37	37
04	Nadpur	1	6	6	31	31
Total	Four (4) PHC	4	35	31	186	186

Table-04, (Source: CHC, Betanati block, Mayurbhanj, Odisha, Date-06/07/22)

1.4.2 Role of ICDS in Betanati Block: The Integrated Child Development Service (Scheme) is a Govt. sponsored scheme running in the block for providing children and women health facility like: Supplementary nutrition, Pre-School education, Health Check-up, referral services, Immunization, Home visit, Nutrition & Health education at village level and early childhood cure & education and Poshan Abhiyaan with curriculum of UNICEF. Under this scheme the 282 ICDS centres, 212 nos. of Helpers, 272 nos. of Workers, 12004 children and 2271 mothers are getting benefits and the detailed report is given below:

Figures of ICDS

Sl. No	Center Nos.	Helper Nos.	Worker Nos.	Child Nos.	Pregnant/Lactating Mother Nos.
01	33	22	32	1536	248
02	36	26	35	1363	243
03	40	29	37	1600	286
04	39	33	36	1468	309
05	41	33	41	1812	351
06	34	22	32	1598	324
07	32	24	32	1414	284
08	27	23	27	1213	226
Total	282	212	272	12004	2271

Table-05, (Source: ICDS Dept, Betanati block, Mayurbhanj, Odisha, Date-10/07/22)

1.4.3 Status of BPGY (Biju Pucca Ghar Yojana) from 2016-17 to 2018-19:

Biju Pucca Ghar Yojana is the state's own flagship programme. The scheme was launched during the financial year in 2014-15 replacing the old scheme 'MO-KUDIA YOJANA' with a view to achieving the objectives of converting all the kutcha houses to Pucca houses.

Status of BPGY at Betanati Block

SL/No	Panchayat Name	BPGY Target	Total completed	Solar light	Drinking Water
01	Ambagadia	32	26	8	32
02	Agria	35	33	17	70
03	Baisinga	55	41	21	50
04	Anla	24	23	10	42
05	Gadadeulia	27	24	11	32
06	Betnoti	42	33	23	34
07	Dahikoti	36	28	10	37
08	Chanchhipada	15	14	06	25
09	Kalama	35	31	8	122
10	Hatijhuri	0	0	06	43
11	Kendua	0	0	13	87
12	Jugal	21	19	06	97
13	Nadpur	20	16	13	62
14	Mahisasole	17	15	6	43
15	Merda	32	26	8	45
16	Muktapur	21	17	7	63
17	Raghupur	28	19	9	52
18	Patalipura	29	25	15	38
19	Purunia	24	19	14	78
20	Purinda	20	18	11	55
21	Salabani (S) Nahandasole	19	18	06	37
22	Sathilo	37	32	6	109
23	Santara	45	40	14	112
24	Saitpur	17	15	7	43
Total	Total	593	532	255	1408

Table-06, (Source: Rural Development Dept, Betanati block, Mayurbhanj, Odisha, Date-10/07/22)

1.4.4 Information of OLM: Odisha Livelihoods Mission (OLM) is a government run project to empower women by generating their livelihoods by various trainings. OLM is the centrally sponsored scheme with a proportionate ratio of 60:40 between Centre and State. OLM has put in place a dedicated and sensitive support structure, to take the rural poor households out of poverty line through capacity building, financial assistance and self-reliant institutions. (<https://odishalivelihoodsmision.in>).

Basic information of OLM:

Total no. of SHG-2205

Existing SHG-1024

New SHG-1181

Target for Bank linkage physical-1140, Financial-3648 lakh.

No of producer groups-8

GP level nursery convergence with MNREGA target-24, on going-5

Details report of OLM,

Scheme	Target	Achievement
Nutrition garden	198	198
Revolving fund	186	101
Mahila Kisan	200	210
DDUGKY	288	288
RSETI (Rural Self Employment Training Institute)	7	2

Table-07 (Source: Block Project Coordinator, Block Development Office, Betanoti block, Mayurbhanj, Date-08/07/22)

1.4.5 NSAP (National Social Assistance Programme): Every relates issues about NSAP of Betanati block described in the following table:

Table-38

SL/No.	Scheme name	Benefited Number	Details
1	IGNOAP	4059	Above 60-79 years received 500/- per months and 80+ years age received 700/- rupees.
2	IGNWP	2491	Above 40 years received 500/- rupees.
3	IGNDP	385	80% criteria received 700/- rupees.
4	NFBS	62	20,000/- rupees received one time.

Table-08 (Source: Block Development Office, Betanati block, Mayurbhanj, Date-08/07/22)

1.5 Significance of the study: Kushmandi Block (C.D.B) and Betanati block are economically backward blocks of India. In these blocks poverty and unemployment are increasing day by day. There is no small industry in these two blocks. As a result, the common people are going to different states in searching of work. Grameen cottage industry has not been developed in the study areas. Most of the people are depended on the agricultural sector because agriculture is the main base of economy to the living people of these rural areas. Some young generations go to different states for work for their livelihood. Specially Paddy is cultivated only once a year in Betanati block. Normally, due to the very poor working conditions of agriculture common people go to other states after cultivating Paddy once a year.

In a hierarchical order, the central and the state governments and also the Panchayats are trying in different ways to improve the regions through varieties of developmental schemes

under the projects of rural development programmes. The significance of research work is to explore some current rural development schemes and their functioning in the study areas.

1.6 Conclusion: In this article total ten (10) rural development schemes have been selected for the study. The study emphasizes on the functioning and progress of rural development schemes in the study areas. Both the Central and the State government are facing the problems of initiating and accelerating the pace of development to enhance the standard of living of the rural people. Good governance occupies a key role in the formulation and implementation of rural development programmes therefore, the success and failure of development efforts to a large extent depend upon the role performed by the bureaucracy, political representatives and the common people in this process.

References:

- Kamal, Mostafa. (2012), Good Governance and Panchayat Raj: Role of Women in Tripura, Ph. D. thesis, Tripura University, 2012, p. 27.*
- Sarkar. Samaresh. Rural Development Programmes in India: Problems and Prospects- A Case Study on Kushmandi Block (Community Development Block) in the District of Dakshin Dinajpur. M.Phil Dissertation, University of Gour Banga, (2018), pp-48-51.*
- Pattanaik, B.K, Rudiments of Rural Development, Sage Texts, New Delhi, 2022.*
- Census of India 2011, West Bengal, Series 20, Part XII A, District Census Handbook, Dakshin Dinajpur.*
- Census of India 2011, Odisha, Series 22, Part XII B, District Census Handbook, Mayurbhanj.*
- Annual Activity Report, ST & ST Development, Minorities & Backward Classes Welfare Department, Govt. of Odisha, 2019-20.*
- Annual Activity Report, Rural Development Department, Bhubaneswar, Govt. of Odisha, 2017-18.*
- Activity Report, Department of Agriculture & Farmers' Empowerment, Govt. of Odisha, 2017-18*
- Annual Activity Report, Department of Women & Child Development and Mission Shakti, Govt. of Odisha, 2019-20.*
- Annual Activity Report, Food Supplies & Consumer Welfare Department, Govt. of Odisha, 2019-20.*
- <https://odishalivehoodsmmission.in>, 04/06/23